

FORMULATION AND OPTIMIZATION OF GOAT MILK CHEESE USING CALCIUM CHLORIDE FOR ENHANCED FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES TARGETING HYPERTENSION AND CARDIOVASCULAR HEALTH

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Abstract

Goat milk is a source of probiotics and helpful for improving the immunity level, also effective against cardiovascular diseases and even from cancer. Cheese is a fermented dairy product which is full of nutrients, soft in texture, white in color and pleasant in taste. So, the current study was designed to optimize the pasteurization temperature and CaCl₂ contents for the development of goat milk cheese. Soft goat milk cheese was prepared with different pasteurization temperature (63, 65, 67 and 70°C for 30, 20, 10, and 1 minute) and with different concentration of CaCl₂ (0.1, 0.2 and 0.3%). After production of cheese, physicochemical properties were observed. Then sensory evaluation of product was done to see the cheese consumer acceptability. After that data taken from the research studies was analyzed statistically. It was analyzed that the protein, texture profile, pH and ash contents of goat milk cheese increased while the fat, moisture contents, yield and sensory attributes decreased from T₁ to T₃. Protein increased from 14.60 to 14.68, ash increased from 3.31 to 4.02, texture profile increased from 3.4 to 3.88 and pH increased from 6.35 to 6.39. On the other hand fat decreased from 20.25 to 19.52, moisture content decreased from 59.83 to 58.82%, yield decreased from 73.217 to 69.063, color appearance decreased from 8.41 to 7.70, taste decreased from 8.26 to 7.53, texture decreased from 8.33 to 6.66, flavor decreased from 8.26 to 6.55, overall acceptability decreased from 8.03 to 7.00 respectively.

INTRODUCTION

The livestock and agriculture sectors have a huge effect on Pakistan's economy by addressing the dietary needs of human beings. Buffalo is rated first (3.3 million ton), cow second (1.9 million ton), goat third (8.7 million ton) camel fourth (8.6 million ton) and sheep fifth (0.39 million ton) in milk production. The largest number of heads

with a total of 70.3 million was secured during the economic year 2015-2016, while buffalo 36.6, cow 42.8, sheep 29.8 million and camel 1.0 million were secured (Pant, 2016).

Cheese is a fermented and concentrated milk base products which are produced in ripened and un-ripened forms (Yangilar, 2013). Goat cheese is one

of the fastest growing types of cheese in the United States today. Chevre production in the northeast region of the United States has therefore steadily increased for the past 10 years. Cheese's consistency and production capacity are partially dictated by the overall quality of the milk used in its preparation. A series of factors, including skin color, individual variation, diet, season, lactation stage and environment, affect the chemical composition of Goat's milk (Goetsch, Zeng, & Gipson, 2011). The agricultural economy of several countries, such as Spain, Greece and France, relies heavily on the goat population and its milk production. Between 1991 to 2014, the number of heads of goat and milk production rose by 69% and 86% worldwide, respectively (Fao, 2018).

Goat is known to be a source of meat and milk for people living in rural areas. Milk obtained from goat is 2% of the total milk production, which helps to treat some of the disorders and provides economic benefits to poor farmers. Persons who are allergic and prone to cow's milk will use goat's milk easily. Owing to its improved digestively, buffering and other curative benefits of goat milk in human medicine, goat milk is distinct from cow's or human milk. Goat milk can be used for the substitution of cow's and human milk in the case of children with a maternal milk deficiency (breast-feeding) (Zenebe, Ahmed, Kabeta, & Kebede, 2014). Within goat's milk, high levels of vitamin A and vitamin B but less Beta-carotene are contained because of conversion into retinol. The color of goat milk is whiter when opposed to cow milk because of this change. People with cow milk allergy or those with gastrointestinal problems may drink goat's milk (De Gobba, Espejo-Carpio, Skibsted, & Otte, 2014; de Sousa et al., 2015).

Environment, stage of lactation, season, breed and individual differences has great impact on physicochemical properties of goat milk (Kljajevic et al., 2018). Seasonal behavior is one of the major factors that has great impact in variation of milk. Throughout early lactation periods, the total substances in goat's milk (fat, sugar, ash and non-fat solid) are stronger, but tend to decrease as time increases. Total solids rise in the last stage lactation but at that time the milk yield remains constant

with small changes (Goetsch et al., 2011). And the chemical structure in the casein micelles in bovine milk and caprine milk are both substantially different.

The maturation of cheese involves a variety of micro-organism and enzyme activity-catalyzed phenomena. It is especially important for proteolysis and lipolysis as they induce changes to the structure of cheese, and the development of taste (Fox, Guinee, Cogan, & McSweeney, 2017). (Yangilar, 2013) addressed safety and lipolysis of goat milk. The scientist investigated the essential considerations and approaches used for studying these biological phenomena. A study was also placed in which scientist examined the effect of the 4 ° C handling of fresh caprine milk cheese in terms of both SDS-PAGE and rheology proteolysis. In soft goat milk cheese from 14 to 28 days shelf time, (Masotti, Battelli, & De Noni, 2012) studied the evolution of the organic acid profile.

The characteristic taste of cheese is an important quality item for cheese producers because the aroma, i.e. the scent and sense of taste when eaten, takes a special role among the other organoleptic components including color or rheological properties. This distinctive taste of a cheese variety comes from a complex combination of volatile and non-volatile chemicals obtained from milk fat, protein and carbohydrates in the process of ripening. These modifications are accompanied by a series of catabolic secondary reactions, responsible for the distinctive fragrance sequence of a certain number of cheeses. The characteristic taste of goat's milk is mostly attributed to compounds that are volatile (Delgado, González-Crespo, Cava, & Ramírez, 2011). The aim of this study is to develop a protocol for producing high-quality goat milk cheese and determine the optimal processing conditions that maximize yield, improve texture, and enhance flavor profile.

Materials and method

2.1 Procurement of raw material

Dairy milk was obtained from Dairy Farm of University of Agriculture, Faisalabad. Curd formation enzyme coagulant Rennet was procured from CHR-HANSEN (CHR-HANSEN Inc,

Denmark). All the chemicals and reagents were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich.

2.2 Treatment Plan

Treatments	CaCl ₂ (%)
T ₁	0.1
T ₂	0.2
T ₃	0.3

Figure 2.1 Different processing steps for the preparation of goat milk cheese

2.3 Physico chemical Analysis

2.3.1 pH

For measuring the pH of goat's milk and cheese, the WTW 82362 pH meter was used in a recommended procedure by (Ong, Soodam, Kentish, Powell, & Gras, 2015). The pH meter was standardized with the pH buffer pH 7 and 4. The milk in a beaker was 20 ml and the electrode in that milk was immersed and the pH value was detected.

2.3.2 Acidity

The titrated method defined in the (Poitevin, 2016) was used to determine milk acidity. The sample contained 10 ml of milk in a beaker and was mixed with this sample by 2-3 drops of phenolphthalein. It was then titrated against 0.1 N NaOH and the quantity of solution used was noted when a pink color came into sight. Milk percent acidity was calculated with the use of the

$$\text{Moisture \%} = \frac{\text{Weigh of china dish} - \text{Weigh of china dish and sample after moisture removal}}{\text{Weigh of dish with cheese sample} - \text{Weigh of dish}} \times 100$$

2.3.4 Fat content

The instruments and reagents required for the analysis included isoamyl alcohol, sulphuric acid, distilled water, a butyrometer, and a centrifugation machine. A 3-gram cheese and 3ml milk sample was weighed into a butyrometer and mixed with 8 ml of warm distilled water. Then, 1 ml of isoamyl alcohol was added. The butyrometer was placed in a centrifugal machine and centrifuged for 5 minutes at 1100 rpm. After centrifugation, the sample was removed, and the fat percentage was determined directly from the butyrometer scale. The fat content was calculated as a percentage of the sample weight, with minor adjustments made as required by the specific method (Gantner, Mijić, Baban, Škrtić, & Turalija, 2015).

2.3.5 Protein content

(Ben-Gigirey, Rodriguez-Velasco, & Gago-Martinez, 2012) approach was used to assess the protein content of milk and cheese. A 10 ml sample of milk and 2g of cheese was digested

sample N/10 NaOH volume x 0.009/ Sample weight x 100.

2.3.3 Moisture content

The moisture content of the goat milk cheese was determined using a hot-air oven maintained at 103 ± 2 °C until a constant weight was achieved, as per the (Poitevin, 2016) method. Sufficient sand was placed in a China dish and heated in the hot-air oven at 103°C for one hour. The dish was then removed, transferred to a desiccator to cool, and its weight was recorded as W1. Approximately 2g of cheese sample (W2) was added to the prepared dish. The dish was carefully placed in the hot-air oven and dried for 5 hours at 103 °C. After drying, the dish was cooled in a desiccator and weighed. This process of heating, cooling, and weighing was repeated promptly until a constant weight was obtained, which was recorded as W3.

using 20-30 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid and a digestion tablet in a digestion tube. The digested sample was cooled, transferred to a 250 ml volumetric flask, and mixed thoroughly for 30 minutes with 100 ml of distilled water. The solution was then diluted to the mark with more distilled water. A 10 ml aliquot of this digested solution was placed in a distillation tube with 10 ml of 40% NaOH and inserted into the Kjeldahl distillation apparatus. The liberated ammonia was distilled over and trapped in a 10% boric acid solution containing a few drops of methyl red indicator. The boric acid trap, initially pink, turned yellow upon absorbing the ammonia. Distillation continued for 2-3 minutes to ensure complete ammonia transfer. The trapped ammonia solution was then titrated with 0.1 N sulfuric acid, and the volume of acid used was recorded. The entire procedure was performed in triplicate to ensure accuracy. Ammonia is expressed as nitrogen that can be measured by nitrogen (%) by using the following formula:

$$\text{Nitrogen (\%)} = \frac{\text{Vol. of H}_2\text{SO}_4 \text{ used (ml)} \times 250 \times 0.0014}{\text{Vol. used for digestion} \times \text{Vol. of digested sample}} \times 100$$

The total protein content is measured in percent by multiplying percent nitrogen with 6.38 factor.

2.3.6 Ash content

A 5 mL sample of milk and a 5g sample of cheese were placed in separate crucibles and their moisture was evaporated by drying on a steam bath. The dried samples were then asked in a muffle furnace at 550 °C until carbon-free ash was obtained. Ash content was measured by the (Srigley & Mossoba, 2017) notified process.

$$\text{Ash (\%)} = \frac{\text{Residual weight}}{\text{Sample weight}} \times 100$$

2.3.7 Cheese yield

The cheese yield was calculated according to the formula given below:

$$\text{Cheese yield} = \frac{\text{Weigh of goat milk cheese}}{\text{weigh of milk for cheese making}} \times 100$$

2.4 Sensory analysis

The samples of goat milk cheese were evaluated based on taste, color, texture, flavor and overall acceptance as defined by (Clark, Costello, Drake, & Bodyfelt, 2009).

2.5 Texture analysis

The texture analysis of goat milk cheese samples in cube shape were analyzed by following the method of (Timothy P Guinee & Kilcawley, 2017), on a texture profile at room temperature with levels of 20 mm / min. Compression force was used for pressing the cheese cubes

2.6 Statistical analysis

The above data was statistically analyzed by using ANOVA with one factorials under CRD with level of significance 95% (Montgomery, 2017).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Physicochemical analysis of goat milk

Chemical compositional evidence from other results which may contain many considerations such as animal breed, seasonal variability, species and water intakes, or feeding habits of animals responsible for compositional diversity in goat's milk. The result of physio chemical analysis of goat milk is expressed in table 3.2. Moatsou & Park (2017) stated that fat content in goat milk is 3-5%. In previous experiments, protein levels could range between 2.4 and 4.1%. Ash content is the organic component found in milk that can usually be measured by burning of inorganic matter that is commonly defined as a mineral. The ash contents of goat's milk vary between 0.69 and 0.74% was observed. And authors also observed that total goat milk solids range from 11.99 to 13.45%. Fat, protein, total solids and ash content of goat milk used in the processing of cheese are identical to the Moatsou & Park (2017). There are variations in the total solids of goat milk which can be caused by changes in fat, protein, lactose and mineral milk content. Changes in the composition of goat milk can be attributable to seasonal fluctuations and genotypes in animals. It was reported that the pH for goat's milk falls between 6.61 and 6.85, and milk acidity is specified as the volume of the dairy lactic acid that is 0.13-0.16% available.

3.1 Physico-chemical analysis of goat milk

Analysis	Goat milk
pH	6.62±0.03
Acidity	0.18±0.01
Fat	3.9±0.05
Protein	3.2±0.09

Ash	0.72±0.01
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3.2 Determination of Fat contents in goat milk cheese

Cunha et al. (2013) suggested that the fat content of cheese improves the taste, shape, color and flavor of towards by jeopardizing the interstitial structure and network of minerals and proteins. Fat content of milk can also influence the functional properties and processing parameters of the cheese. The effects of calcium chloride on cheese ash are mentioned in Table 3.2. Different values of fat were in range from 19.520 to 20.253%. The highest value of fat was observed in T₁ which was 20.253%, while the lowest value of fat was observed in T₃ which was 19.520%. Addition of different concentration of calcium chloride during cheese making highly affected the fat of cheese sample. However, it is apparent from data interaction between the samples and calcium chloride presented the highly significant effect on cheese fat. According to means of treatment T₁ (20.253 ±0.43), T₂ (19.720 ±0.50), T₃ (19.520 ±0.041) are decreasing.

The result of study was opposite to the results of cheddar cheese given by Ong et al. (2015) explained that fat was decreasing by increasing the concentrations of calcium chloride in cheddar cheese. They used various concentrations of calcium chloride like (0, 50, 100, 200, 300, 600 mg/l) in the cheddar cheese. It was observed from the results that by increasing the concentrations of calcium chloride in the cheddar cheese there was slightly changes in the fat value of the cheese.

3.3 Determination of Protein contents in goat milk cheese

Guinee et al. (2006) stated that high protein content in milk will lead to higher yield of cheese. They proposed that casein or proteins are the key components of milk responsible for metabolic improvements through the processing and ripening of final cheese content. Santos et al. 2016 documented protein content for fresh cream goat milk cheese which values are in accordance with the present study. The effects of calcium chloride on cheese protein are mentioned in Table 3.2. Different values of protein were in range of 14.607

to 14.687%. The highest value of protein was observed in T₃ which was 14.687%, while the lowest value of color was observed in T₁ which was 14.607%. Addition of different concentration of calcium chloride during cheese making had not affected the protein of cheese sample. However, it is apparent from data interaction between the samples and calcium chloride presented the Non-significant effect on protein of cheese. According to means of treatment T₁ (14.607 ±0.042), T₂ (14.631 ±0.61), T₃ (14.687 ±0.45) are increasing. The result of study was compared to the results of cheddar cheese given by Ong, Dagastine, Kentish, & Gras (2013). who explained that protein was decreased by increasing the concentrations of calcium chloride in the cheddar cheese. He used various concentrations of calcium chloride like (0, 50, 100, 200, 300, 600 mg/l) in the cheddar cheese. It was observed from the results that by increasing the concentrations of calcium chloride in the cheddar cheese there was slight changes on the protein value of the cheese.

3.4 Determination of Ash contents in goat milk cheese

Inorganic traces can be referred to as ash material after the oxidation or inflammation of organic matter of the product. The elements found in ash have been converted into carbonates or oxides from their original state after oxidation of the organic material. Ash content in milk that induces ion strength and gel formation as well as a high amount of calcium (Sant’Ana et al., 2013).

The effects of calcium chloride on cheese ash are mentioned in Figure 1. Different values of ash were in range of 3.313 to 4.026%. The highest value of ash was observed in T₃ which was 4.0267%, while the lowest value of ash was observed in T₁ which was 3.313%. Addition of different concentration of calcium chloride during cheese making highly affected the ash of cheese sample. However, it is apparent from data interaction between the samples and calcium chloride presented the highly significant effect on cheese ash. According to means of treatment T₁

(3.3133 \pm 0.12), T₂ (3.6267 \pm 0.12), T₃ (4.026 \pm 0.040) are increasing.

Abdalla & Ahmed (2010) stated that ash content was significantly decreased by increasing the concentrations of calcium chloride in the white cheese. Different concentration of calcium chloride (0.02%, 0.04%) was used. It was concluded from the results that by increasing the concentrations of calcium chloride in the white cheese there was significantly decrease in the ash content of the cheese.

3.5 Determination of moisture contents in goat milk cheese

The moisture content is one of the key characteristics that contributes to cheese's plasticization effect. Protein components present in milk make it less elastic and more vulnerable to breakage by application of force (Frau, Font de Valdez, & Pece, 2014). Moisture determination is the main criterion for cheese quality assessment. The product's shelf life and texture vary with moisture shift with the finished product (Kim et al., 2018). The effects of calcium chloride on moisture of cheese are mentioned in Table 3.2. Different values of moisture were in range of 59.837 to 58.823%. The highest value of moisture was observed in T₁ was 59.837% while the lowest value of moisture observed in T₃ which was 58.823%. Addition of different concentration of calcium chloride during cheese making highly affected the moisture of cheese sample. However, it is apparent from data interaction between the samples and calcium chloride presented the highly significant effect on moisture of cheese. According to means of treatment T₁ (59.837 \pm 0.33), T₂ (59.310 \pm 0.81), T₃ (58.823 \pm 1.24) are decreasing. Ong et al. (2013) demonstrated that moisture was decreased by increasing the concentrations of calcium chloride in cheddar cheese. The result of study was compared to the results of cheddar cheese. He used various concentrations of calcium chloride at ratio of (0, 50, 100, 200, 300, 600 mg/l) in the cheddar cheese. It was determined from the results that by increasing the concentrations of calcium chloride in the cheddar cheese there was slight changes on the moisture of the cheese.

3.6 Determination of pH in goat milk cheese

The effects of calcium chloride on pH of cheese are mentioned in Table 3.2. Different values of pH were in range of 6.356 to 6.396. The highest value of pH was observed in T₃ 6.396 while the lowest value of texture profile was observed at T₁ 6.356. Addition of different concentration of calcium chloride during cheese making highly affected the pH of cheese sample. However, it is apparent from data interaction between the samples and calcium chloride presented the highly significant effect on pH of cheese. According to means of treatment T₁ (6.356 \pm 0.05), T₂ (6.383 \pm 0.10), T₃ (6.396 \pm 0.15) are increasing.

The result of research was opposite to the results of cheddar cheese given by Ong et al. (2013). who explained that pH was constant by increasing the concentrations of calcium chloride in the cheddar cheese. Various concentrations of calcium chloride (0, 50, 100, 200, 300, 600 mg/L) were used in the production of cheddar cheese. The results indicated that increasing the calcium chloride concentration did not produce a significant change in the pH of the cheese.

3.7 Texture profile analysis

Texture helps in recognizing and defining cheese origin. In the relation of sensory texture, solid and semi-solid foods have different properties. Improper quality adds to consumer disapproval of the product. The effects of calcium chloride on texture profile of cheese are mentioned in Table 3.2. Different values of texture profile were in range of 3.40 to 3.88 Pa. The highest value of texture profile was observed in T₃ at 3.88 while the lowest value of texture profile was observed in T₁ at 3.40 Pa. Addition of different concentration of calcium chloride during cheese making highly affected the texture profile of cheese sample. However, it is apparent from data interaction between the samples and calcium chloride presented the highly significant effect on texture profile of cheese. According to means of treatment T₁ (3.40 \pm 0.10), T₂ (3.47 \pm 0.15), T₃ (3.88 \pm 0.12) are increasing.

Ong et al. (2013) demonstrated that by adding calcium chloride in cheese, the texture of cheese will be affected. Various concentrations of calcium

chloride (0, 50, 100, 200, 300, 600 mg/L) were used in the production of cheddar cheese. The results indicated that increasing calcium chloride concentration did not produce a significant change in the texture of the cheese. But cheese made with 100mg/l of calcium chloride had a significant effect on texture profile of cheese. Similar results were obtained by Soodam et al. (2015) shows that adding calcium chloride and lowering draining pH reduces protein breakdown and porosity during cheese ripening. These adjustments help modify the process without harming the final cheese quality. Another study by Guinee et al. (2002) found that calcium level and pH strongly affect Mozzarella’s texture and meltability. Lower calcium and lower pH both increased moisture, matrix hydration, stretchability, and flow, while higher calcium made cheese firmer and less meltable.

3.8 Yield

Cheese obtained from 100 liters / kg of milk may be classified as the yield of the cheese. In terms of profitability for the food industry, yield is one of the major characteristics of a product. The more solid in the milk, cheese yield will be higher, and the more economic benefits for the food industry

would eventually appear. The effects of calcium chloride on yield of cheese are mentioned in table 3.2. Different values of yield were in range of 69.063 to 73.217. The highest value of yield was observed in T₁ at 73.217 while the lowest value of yield was observed in T₃ at 69.063. Addition of different concentration of calcium chloride during cheese making highly affected the yield of cheese sample. However, it is apparent from data interaction between the samples and calcium chloride that it presented the highly significant effect on taste of cheese. According to means of treatment T₁ (73.217 ±0.10), T₂ (72.333 ±0.11), T₃ (69.063 ±0.17) are decreasing.

Frau et al. (2014) reported that yield of goat cheese decreases by increasing the amount of calcium chloride. He also added calcium chloride while making goat cheese at concentration of 0.01% and 0.02%. It was concluded that yield of goat cheese was higher when he added 0.01% calcium chloride. And when he added 0.02% concentration of calcium chloride, the yield became low. Hence it showed that by increasing the concentration of calcium chloride, yield of goat cheese decreases.

Table 3.2 Effect of Calcium Chloride on the different parameters of goat milk cheese

Parameter	Treatments		
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃
Fat contents (%)	20.253 ±0.43 ^a	19.720 ±0.50 ^b	19.520 ±0.41 ^c
Protein contents (%)	14.607 ±0.42 ^c	14.631 ±0.61 ^b	14.687 ±0.45 ^a
Ash contents (%)	3.3133 ±0.12 ^c	3.6267 ±0.12 ^b	4.026 ±0.040 ^a
Moisture contents (%)	59.837 ±0.33 ^a	59.310 ±0.81 ^b	58.823 ±1.24 ^c
pH	6.3567 ±0.05 ^c	6.3833 ±0.1 ^b	6.3967 ±0.15 ^a
Texture (Pa)	3.40 ±0.10 ^c	3.47 ±0.15 ^b	3.88 ±0.12 ^a
Yield (%)	73.217 ±0.10 ^a	72.333 ±0.11 ^b	69.063 ±0.17 ^c

T₁= Goat milk at 0.1% concentration of Calcium Chloride

T₂= Goat milk at 0.2% concentration of Calcium Chloride

T₃= Goat milk at 0.3% concentration of Calcium Chloride

3.9 Sensory Evaluation of goat milk cheese

3.9.1 Color

Regarding quality parameter, color is considered as most important sensation which is perceived by

consumer. Discoloration in the product may be considered as defect in quality. Animal diet season and type of milk like goat, camel, buffalo and cow reflects the color of cheese.

The effects of calcium chloride on color of cheese are mentioned in Figure 1. Different values of taste were in range of 7.70 to 8.41. The highest value of color was observed in T₁ at 8.41 while the lowest value of color was observed in T₃ at 7.70. Addition of different concentration of calcium chloride during cheese making had not affected the color of cheese sample. However, it is apparent from data interaction between the samples and calcium chloride presented the Non-significant effect on color of cheese. According to means of treatment T₁ (8.41 ±0.38), T₂ (8.26 ±0.30), T₃ (7.70 ±0.65) are decreasing. The results of this research were like the results of goat milk cheese given by Funahashi & Horiuchi (2008). He concluded that by addition of calcium chloride in goat milk cheese, the sensory attribute (color) was decreased. Various concentration of calcium chloride was used by Funahashi & Horiuchi (2008) at rate of 0.01% and 0.02%. He concluded from the result that by addition of 0.01% calcium chloride in the goat cheese, goat cheese had more color. When he added 0.02% calcium chloride in the goat cheese the color of goat cheese became lite. Hence, it was demonstrated that by increasing the concentration of calcium chloride there was decrease in the value of the color of goat cheese.

3.9.2 Taste

Sensory parameter which is perceived through taste buds presented on tongue is classified as taste which is also an important parameter for the acceptability of product. Biochemicals and microbiological processes are the main causes for the flavor and taste development in cheese during storage and ripening. These processes improve flavor and taste because of the enzymatic digestion of the curd happening during storage (Zisu & Shah, 2006).

The effects of calcium chloride on taste of cheese are mentioned in Figure 1. Different values of taste were in range of 7.53 to 8.26. The highest value of taste was observed in T₁ at 8.26 while the lowest value of taste was observed in T₃ at 7.53. Addition of different concentration of calcium chloride during cheese making highly affected the texture of cheese sample. However, it is apparent from data interaction between the samples and

calcium chloride that it presented the highly significant effect on taste of cheese. According to means of treatment T₁ (8.26 ±0.25), T₂ (7.76 ±0.25), T₃ (7.53 ±0.25) are decreasing. Fuxin (2002) represented that when the concentrations of calcium chloride increased in the goat cheese the sensory attribute (taste) was decreased gradually. The use of various calcium chloride concentrations (0.01% and 0.02%) in goat milk cheese revealed that the 0.01% treatment (T₁) produced a superior taste.

3.9.3 Texture

Texture helps in recognizing and defining cheese origin. In the connection of sensory texture, solid and semi-solid foods have different properties. Inadequate texture leads to customer disapproval of the product. The effects of calcium chloride on overall acceptability of cheese are mentioned in Figure 1. Different values of texture were in range of 6.66 to 8.33. The highest value of texture was observed in T₁ at 8.33 while the lowest value of texture was observed in T₃ at 6.55. Addition of different concentration of calcium chloride during cheese making highly affected the texture of cheese sample. However, it is apparent from data interaction between the samples and calcium chloride presented the highly significant effect on texture of cheese. According to means of treatment T₁ (8.33 ±0.38), T₂ (7.60 ±0.36), T₃ (6.66 ±0.15) are decreasing.

The results of research were like the results of goat milk cheese given by Golinelli et al. (2014). Various concentrations of calcium chloride (0.01% and 0.02%) were tested in goat milk cheese. The results indicated that as the concentration increased, the sensory attribute of texture gradually decreased. Specifically, the 0.01% concentration (T₁) produced a stronger texture, while the higher 0.02% concentration resulted in a weaker tone. Hence, it was demonstrated that by increasing the concentration of calcium chloride there was decrease in the value of the texture of goat cheese. T₁ showed the best as compared to T₂.

3.9.4 Flavor

Regarding quality parameter, flavor is also considered as an important sensation which is perceived by consumer for cheese by smelling, bulkiness and testing. Acceptance of the product is critically depending on the flavor. Biochemical and micro biological process are the main causes for the flavor development in cheese during storage and ripening. These processes improve flavor due to enzymatic activity like lipolysis, glycolysis and proteolysis. The effects of calcium chloride on overall acceptability of cheese are mentioned in Figure 1. Different flavors were in range of 6.55 to 8.26. The highest value for flavor was observed in T₁ at 8.26 while the lowest value of flavor was observed at T₃ 6.55. Addition of different concentration of calcium chloride during cheese making slightly affected the flavor of cheese sample. However, it is apparent from data interaction between the samples and calcium chloride presented the highly significant effect on flavor of cheese. According to means of treatment T₁ (8.26 ±0.25), T₂ (7.23 ±0.25), T₃ (6.55 ±0.37) are decreasing. Egypto et al., (2013) represented that when the concentrations of calcium chloride increased in the goat cheese the sensory attribute (flavor) decreased gradually. The use of various calcium chloride concentrations (0.01% and 0.02%) in goat milk cheese revealed that the 0.01% treatment (T₁) produced a stronger flavor. In contrast, the higher 0.02% concentration resulted in a less intense flavor profile. Hence, it was demonstrated that by increasing the concentration of calcium chloride there was decrease in the value of the flavor of goat cheese. So, T₁ showed the best results as compared to T₂. The results of research were like the results of goat milk cheese given by Golinelli et al. (2014).

3.9.5 Overall acceptability

Overall acceptability is the final quality parameter of cheese other than color, texture, flavor and taste. The effects of calcium chloride on overall acceptability of cheese are mentioned in figure 1. Different values of overall acceptability were in range of 7.00 to 8.03. The highest value for overall acceptability was observed in T₁ at 8.03 while the lowest value for overall acceptability was observed in T₃ at 7.00. Addition of different concentration of calcium chloride during cheese making slightly affected the overall acceptability of cheese sample. However, it is apparent from data interaction between the samples and calcium chloride presented the significant effect on overall acceptability of cheese. According to means of treatment T₁ (8.03±0.15), T₂ (7.76±0.30), T₃ (7.00±0.2) are decreasing. Bille et al. (2001) represented that when the concentrations of calcium chloride increased in the goat cheese, the sensory attribute (overall acceptability) was decreased gradually. He used the various concentrations of calcium chloride at rate of 0.01% and 0.02% in goat milk cheese. He culminated from the results that, by addition of 0.01% calcium chloride to the goat cheese (T₁) has much more overall acceptability. And added 0.02% calcium chloride to the goat cheese the overall acceptability of goat cheese became low. Hence, it was demonstrated that by increasing the concentration of calcium chloride there was decrease in the value of the overall acceptability of goat cheese. So, T₁ showed the best results as compared to T₂ and T₃. The results of research were like the results of goat milk cheese given by Bille et al. (2001).

Table 3.3 Effect of calcium chloride on sensory profile of goat milk cheese

Parameter	Treatments		
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃
Color	8.41 ±0.38 ^a	8.26 ±0.30 ^b	7.70 ±0.65 ^c
Taste	8.26 ±0.25 ^a	7.76 ±0.25 ^b	7.53 ±0.25 ^c
Texture	8.33 ±0.38 ^a	7.60 ±0.36 ^b	6.66 ±0.15 ^c
Flavor	8.26 ±0.25 ^a	7.23 ±0.25 ^b	6.55 ±0.3 ^c
Overall acceptability	8.03 ±0.15 ^a	7.76 ±0.30 ^b	7.00 ±0.2 ^c

T1= Goat milk at 0.1% concentration of calcium chloride

T2= Goat milk at 0.2% concentration of calcium chloride

T3= Goat milk at 0.3% concentration of calcium chloride

Figure 1 Effect of Calcium Chloride on the Sensory Parameters of goat milk cheese

4. Conclusion and future directions

Based on the detailed study, it was concluded that the use of calcium chloride significantly influences the properties of goat milk cheese. The optimal pasteurization condition was first established at 63°C for 30 minutes. Subsequently, cheese was produced with varying calcium chloride levels (T1=0.01%, T2=0.02%, T3=0.03%). The results demonstrated that as the calcium chloride concentration increased from T1 to T3, the protein, ash, pH, and texture profile values increased, while the fat, moisture content, and cheese yield decreased. The sensory attributes, including color, taste, texture, flavor, and overall acceptability, were all highest in treatment T₁ (0.01% CaCl₂). Statistical analysis confirmed that most parameters, including yield and key sensory traits, were significantly affected, with T₁ consistently outperforming the higher concentrations. Therefore, the addition of 0.01% calcium chloride is recommended for optimizing cheese yield and producing goat milk cheese with superior sensory qualities. Future research should explore the impact of different starter cultures and ripening conditions on the quality and flavor

profile of goat milk cheese. Scaling the optimized process for commercial production and conducting detailed market acceptance studies would be valuable.

5. REFERENCES

- Abdalla, M. O. M., & Ahmed, O. I. (2010). *Effect of heat treatment, level of sodium chloride, calcium chloride on the chemical composition of white cheese.*
- Ben-Gigirey, B., Rodríguez-Velasco, M. L., & Gago-Martínez, A. (2012). Extension of the validation of AOAC official method SM 2005.06 for dc-GTX2, 3: interlaboratory study. *Journal of AOAC International*, 95(1), 111–121.
- Bille, P. G., Hiwelepo, P., & Keya, E. L. (2001). Examining the need for the use of calcium chloride in the processing of Gouda cheese made from pasteurised milk. *Journal of Food Technology in Africa*, 6(2), 44–47.
- Clark, S., Costello, M., Drake, M., & Bodyfelt, F. (2009). *The sensory evaluation of dairy products* (Vol. 571). Springer.

- Cunha, C. R., Grimaldi, R., Alcântara, M. R., & Viotto, W. H. (2013). Effect of the type of fat on rheology, functional properties and sensory acceptance of spreadable cheese analogue. *International Journal of Dairy Technology*, 66(1), 54–62.
- De Gobba, C., Espejo-Carpio, F. J., Skibsted, L. H., & Otte, J. (2014). Antioxidant peptides from goat milk protein fractions hydrolysed by two commercial proteases. *International Dairy Journal*, 39(1), 28–40.
- de Sousa, Y. R. F., da Silva Vasconcelos, M. A., Costa, R. G., de Azevedo Filho, C. A., de Paiva, E. P., & do Egypto, R. de C. R. (2015). Sialic acid content of goat milk during lactation. *Livestock Science*, 177, 175–180.
- Delgado, F. J., González-Crespo, J., Cava, R., & Ramírez, R. (2011). Proteolysis, texture and colour of a raw goat milk cheese throughout the maturation. *European Food Research and Technology*, 233(3), 483–488.
- do Egypto, R. de C. R., Santos, B. M., Gomes, A. M. P., Monteiro, M. J., Teixeira, S. M., de Souza, E. L., ... Pintado, M. M. E. (2013). Nutritional, textural and sensory properties of Coalho cheese made of goats' milk and their mixture. *LWT-Food Science and Technology*, 50(2), 538–544.
- Fao, F. (2018). Food and agriculture organization of the United Nations. Rome, URL: [Http://Faostat.Fao.Org](http://Faostat.Fao.Org), 403.
- Fox, P. F., Guinee, T. P., Cogan, T. M., & McSweeney, P. L. H. (2017). *Fundamentals of cheese science* (Vol. 1). Springer.
- Frau, F., Font de Valdez, G., & Pece, N. (2014). Effect of pasteurization temperature, starter culture, and incubation temperature on the physicochemical properties, yield, rheology, and sensory characteristics of spreadable goat cheese. *Journal of Food Processing*, 2014(1), 705746.
- Funahashi, H., & Horiuchi, J. (2008). Characteristics of the churning process in continuous butter manufacture and modelling using an artificial neural network. *International Dairy Journal*, 18(3), 323–328.
- Gantner, V., Mijić, P., Baban, M., Škrtić, Z., & Turalija, A. (2015). The overall and fat composition of milk of various species. *Mljekarstvo: Časopis Za Unaprijeđenje Proizvodnje i Prerade Mlijeka*, 65(4), 223–231.
- Goetsch, A. L., Zeng, S. S., & Gipson, T. A. (2011). Factors affecting goat milk production and quality. *Small Ruminant Research*, 101(1–3), 55–63.
- Golinelli, L. P., Carvalho, A. C., Casaes, R. S., Lopes, C. S. C., Deliza, R., Paschoalin, V. M. F., & Silva, J. T. (2014). Sensory analysis and species-specific PCR detect bovine milk adulteration of frescal (fresh) goat cheese. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 97(11), 6693–6699.
- Guinee, T. P., Feeney, E. P., Auty, M. A. E., & Fox, P. F. (2002). Effect of pH and calcium concentration on some textural and functional properties of Mozzarella cheese. *Journal of dairy science*, 85(7), 1655–1669.
- Guinee, T. P., O'Kennedy, B. T., & Kelly, P. M. (2006). Effect of milk protein standardization using different methods on the composition and yields of Cheddar cheese. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 89(2), 468–482.
- Guinee, Timothy P., & Kilcawley, K. N. (2017). Ingredient cheese and cheese-based ingredients. In *Cheese* (pp. 715–755). Elsevier.
- Kim, N. H., Lee, N. Y., Kim, M. G., Kim, H. W., Cho, T. J., Joo, I. S., ... Rhee, M. S. (2018). Microbiological criteria and ecology of commercially available processed cheeses according to the product specification and physicochemical characteristics. *Food Research International*, 106, 468–474.

- Kljajevic, N. V., Tomasevic, I. B., Miloradovic, Z. N., Nedeljkovic, A., Miocinovic, J. B., & Jovanovic, S. T. (2018). Seasonal variations of Saanen goat milk composition and the impact of climatic conditions. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 55(1), 299-303.
- Masotti, F., Battelli, G., & De Noni, I. (2012). The evolution of chemical and microbiological properties of fresh goat milk cheese during its shelf life. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 95(9), 4760-4767.
- Moatsou, G., & Park, Y. W. (2017). Goat milk products: Types of products, manufacturing technology, chemical composition, and marketing. *Handbook of Milk of Non-Bovine Mammals*, 84-150.
- Montgomery, D. C. (2017). *Design and analysis of experiments*. John Wiley & sons.
- Ong, L., Dagastine, R. R., Kentish, S. E., & Gras, S. L. (2013). The effect of calcium chloride addition on the microstructure and composition of Cheddar cheese. *International Dairy Journal*, 33(2), 135-141.
- Ong, L., Soodam, K., Kentish, S. E., Powell, I. B., & Gras, S. L. (2015). The addition of calcium chloride in combination with a lower draining pH to change the microstructure and improve fat retention in Cheddar cheese. *International Dairy Journal*, 46, 53-62.
- Pant, K. P. (n.d.). 3.13 Emerging but Fragmented International Markets for Royal Jelly. *Proceeding of Agricultural Marketing Conference*.
- Poitevin, E. (2016). Official methods for the determination of minerals and trace elements in infant formula and milk products: A review. *Journal of AOAC International*, 99(1), 42-52. <https://doi.org/10.5740/jaoacint.15-0246>
- Sant'Ana, A. M. S., Bezerril, F. F., Madruga, M. S., Batista, A. S. M., Magnani, M., Souza, E. L., & Queiroga, R. (2013). Nutritional and sensory characteristics of Minas fresh cheese made with goat milk, cow milk, or a mixture of both. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 96(12), 7442-7453.
- Soodam, K., Ong, L., Powell, I. B., Kentish, S. E., & Gras, S. L. (2015). Effect of calcium chloride addition and draining pH on the microstructure and texture of full fat Cheddar cheese during ripening. *Food Chemistry*, 181, 111-118.
- Srigley, C. T., & Mossoba, M. M. (2017). *Current analytical techniques for food lipids*.
- Yangilar, F. (2013). As a potentially functional food: Goats' milk and products. *Journal of Food and Nutrition Research*, 1(4), 68-81.
- Zenebe, T., Ahmed, N., Kabeta, T., & Kebede, G. (2014). Review on medicinal and nutritional values of goat milk. *Academic Journal of Nutrition*, 3(3), 30-39.
- Zisu, B., & Shah, N. P. (2006). Role of microbial exopolysaccharides on moisture retention, texture and functionality of low-fat mozzarella cheeses. *Australian Journal of Dairy Technology*, 61(3), 253.